

Views of Teachers Regarding the Management and Financial Power: Factors that affect Quality Education in Public Sector at Secondary Schools

Muhammad Tayyab, Muhammad Amjid, Asaf Niwaz, Javed Iqbal

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 14, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: August 30, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Manaement, Financial Power, Quality, Education, Factors, Secondary Schools</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5740839</p>	<p><i>This study aimed to examine the Management and Financial Powers as factors affecting quality education in secondary schools. The objective of the study was to examine the factors that affect quality education in terms of management and financial power in public sector secondary schools. The population of the study comprised of secondary schools and the teachers in the public sector in Mardan Division. There were nine hundred and sixty (960) teachers (480 teachers from District Mardan and 480 teachers from District Swabi) of urban and rural areas were randomly selected from 96 secondary schools and ten teachers from each selected school (10x96=960) constituted the sample of the study. The proportion of boys and girls schools from urban and rural areas was equal. The data was collected from the respondents through the questionnaires and was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical techniques such as frequency, Percentage and ANOVA using SPSS. The findings of the study revealed facilities of scholarships and transportation did not affect quality education. There is an effective school management style that offers a conducive environment for teaching and learning. Teachers have ease of access to the principal to discuss problems, teachers come to the class on time, and teachers leave the class on time are the significant factors of quality education. The quality of physical facilities (proper buildings, sufficient classrooms, labs) affects the quality of education in school.</i></p>

Introduction

If a piece of work is not carried out according to the true potential of the staff's ability, it will compromise the honor of the supervise. Likewise, if a lecture is not ready properly and delivered according to the ability of the teacher, it will lead to compromising on the integrity of the faculty members as well as the educational institution. Quality in education refers to the fact that all the important people in the education system have gotten a focus on the satisfaction of parents and students by doing unceasing efforts to improve the education system. It should, however, be kept in mind that quality in education cannot be viewed as a fixed perception. It is rather a comparative to a specific place, stage as well a learner. Quality education refers to the kind of education that empowers students to cope with those challenges that confront humanity as well as the challenges of the future (Sharma & Kamath, 2006).

Quality education also enables students to come up with practicable solutions to such challenges. It implies that quality education is a dynamic and relative term and regarded quality education yesterday might not fulfill the criteria of what will be considered as quality education tomorrow. This seems quite true today if we consider the fast modifications made because of new technologies. This is the reason that a single definition of quality cannot be agreed upon. As discussed, there is no agreement on a single definition of quality. For something which the organizations do; a procedure to judge the extent to which the aims, goals, and objectives of the organizations have been achieved can be termed as quality. Simplistically put, quality is a managerial tool that improves performance by making significant contributions at the levels of individual subjects, departments, or institutions (Doherty, 2008).

According to UNESCO (1990), quality of education encompasses liberty, numeracy as well as life skills that are instilled by way of curriculum, teachers, content, teaching methodologies, examination system, management as well as administration, and policies. Taking into account such definitions, these are expected that education will make significant contributions towards long-lasting human development. It is hoped that education will improve the quality of life at individual, family, societal, and world levels. UNESCO (2004) claimed that education is a fundamental right of every human being. Therefore taking part in quality education is end in itself because, being a right, education paves the way towards the fulfillment of other rights as well.

EDUCATION SYSTEM IN PAKISTAN

Generally, speaking education is a system of knowledge in which behaviors, skills, knowledge, and values are transferred from one generation to the next generation through the teaching-learning process.

In Pakistan, education has been divided into five categories: Primary/Elementary, i.e. from 1st to grade 5th; Middle, i.e. from 6th to 8th class; Secondary/High i.e. from 9th class to 10th. After the Matric class, school examinations are led by Boards of Intermediate & Secondary Education; and at the university level, higher degrees are awarded (Shami & et.al, 2005). Khyber Pakhtunkhwa is a province of Pakistan, it has seven divisions and thirty-five districts in this province. Mardan division is one of the divisions of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. There are two districts in Mardan division, district Mardan and district Swabi. (Wikipedia, 2020). Public Sector encompasses all those schools whose expenses and salaries of employees are drawn from the national exchequer. The public sector is responsible to educate a great number of students at the payment of the government. Education will be provided free of cost or by taking only a lesser amount of fee. Nations spend the maximum amount of money on educating the masses because, in every sector, they need a certain number of educated people or specialists. Any change whether selected or undesired can be introduced in the minds of the youth through the national curriculum (Wang, 2013). The demand of the society from the public sector is not satisfying in quality education due to various reasons while from the private sector they are fulfilling the demand. The private sector always claims the quality education and that is why it looks pertinent to conduct the study regarding factors affecting quality education in public sector at secondary level in Mardan division.

The present study was conducted in the province of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. Like in other developing countries, Pakistan is also facing problem of deteriorating in provision of quality education in public schools. The private education institutions are growing rapidly in numbers as a profitable business. This is also a bitter fact that teachers working in public schools are better qualified, experienced, well paid and have job security than those teachers working in private schools. It is also alarming that quality of education in public schools is far behind as compared to the quality of education in private educational institutes. It is also observed that heads of the institutions are appointed on the basis of their length of job (seniority in many cases) which results in lowering the quality education. This study was taken into consideration keeping in mind two major factors particularly the management skills and financial powers in the hands of principals of public sector secondary schools in two very prominent districts (Mardan & Swabi). The following were the objectives of the study; to investigate the factors affecting quality education in terms of management in public sector secondary schools; and to investigate the factors affecting quality education in terms of financial power in public sector secondary schools.

Review of Related Literature

The purpose of this study was to find out the factors affecting quality education in secondary schools of Mardan Division, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. This chapter therefore, deals with the views of different scholars about quality education. Thus, most literature on the subject appeared in recent years and studies the factors that help to improve quality education and suggest the ways to promote better teaching and learning in schools.

The school leadership, as well as management, plays a key part to improve the quality of education. Unless the school leadership and management do not adopt meaningful practices and activities, the quality of education is unimaginable (MoE, 2006). As indicated by the Ministry of Education, the school principals got the following duties in the implementation of quality education. These choose the proper timing and period of the course, decide on the making of groups in which teachers will be members, select suitable teachers for the groups and gives an introduction about the course, contacts a close-by school for acting as partner school (for sharing experience).

The directions are given on the course to the members, who are then ready to start the course (Ministry of Education, 2005). As stated by Adesine (1990), the organization, as well as mobilization of all human and material assets in any system for the successful accomplishment and achievement of the set objectives and targets of the system, can be termed as management. In any kind of organization including the educational system, effective management is thought to be essential for the achievement of organizational goals.

Philips (2011) sketched the role of instructional leadership. It demands from a principal to ensure that perfect education effects were framed in each area of the learning, which was to be created on measurable objectives. The allocation of funds to teaching and learning activities was also considered one of his significant responsibilities. He was also responsible for proper scheduling including supervision of teaching and learning events in the school.

However, insufficient funding for student support services, libraries, journals, books, unconditional equipped laboratories, and lack of repair facilities of equipment and nonqualified staff are essential factors in poor education. Salaries and other allowances consume the budget of schools and colleges, thus, little left for the items. Therefore, the fund is very essential for enhancing the quality of education (Kathleen, 2003). Leadership in schools play vital role as principals of the schools are solely responsible for managing all human, physical as well as financial resources (Nyongesa, 2007). Principals' role is very crucial in mobilizing and translating available resources in order to improve school effectiveness by improving students' successes. In Pakistan,

usually principals are appointed on the basis of their length of job (seniority) only while ignoring potential of leadership and this is also true in many other developing countries like in countries of African region. According to Nyamwea (2006), there are limited trainings for financial management skills of heads of the schools or any other support in most of the African countries. According to Government of Kenya (2006), principals of the secondary schools need training on successful management of schools' finances and they must be well conversant to these skills. The schools must have records of all activities for better accountability, enhancement of planning and financial performance. According to Munyiri (2008), account clerks wrote and kept record of finances, they put schools financial statements in general ledger consisting of figures and records reflecting daily use of finances in the schools. Similarly a cash book is another record keeping tools where receipts of cash payments (debit or credit) are recorded at designated places. According to Baraka (2010), experiences heads knowing all about financial managements can perform properly to make schools more effective. Only trainings on different aspects of finances donot serve the purpose as experience does. In preparation of school budget, teachers looking for different budget heads need to involve and to make appropriate decisions (Kuria, 2012).

Theoretical Framework of the Study

Although role of schools' principals is very much crucial in bringing about positive changes in schools and their financial knowledge as well as managerial skills help them in executing their polices with less hardles. Prudential theory argues that everyone in the school in general and the managers (principals) in particular must know how to use schools finances wisely. For a principals to be a prudent means he must be smart enough to utilize all means and resources to achieve maximum goals of the schools. To be a prudents, he requires carefull thinking, fore thought planning and exercising sound judgement to manage the practical affairs of the school. He has to ignore wants and to minimize unproductive cost in terms of money and time. Only this strategy helps hime become a good leaders to make school more effective. Similarly, theory of efficiency also works well in dealing with the financial matters of the schools. According to this theory, principals of the schools must be able to transform inputs at the lowest costs into the highest benefits. It is not possible to have such dynamic persons as principals in every schools. In application of such a little resources which general schools have to get maximum output require capacity building to schools principals in an effective financial management. Another theory of Agency also workable, according to this theory, the principals develop rapport with his/her staff and then develop a team who work according to his/her instructions. This team may be a person or two or may be more than but they will all work as agents of the principal. This theory can easily be applied in public schools. This particular study does not take any single theory to build up methodology but the all of the theories discussed about to develop tools of the research, to analyze data and to reach to the conclusions.

Methodology

The purpose of conducting the current research was to find the factors affecting quality education. tow major aspects e.g., financial powers or autonomy of the principals and their managements was considered to investigate about to what extents these two aspects affect quality of education at secondary schools in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Teachers were the subjects of this study because about utilization of finances of the schools and to find out about the management skills of the principals only teachers may explain well. This study was quantitative and the sample of the study comprised of teachers working in secondary schools of two districts (Mardan and Swabi) of the province of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The geographical area covered by this study was huge so survey as a research design was adopted to conduct this research. The population consisted of 5024 teachers from 297 secondary schools in the public sector in Mardan and Swabi of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (According to Education Management Information System, 2016-17). Out of total two hundred and ninety-seven (297) secondary schools in the public sector from both districts, 96 schools were randomly selected. The proportion of boys and girls schools from urban and rural areas was equal. Nine hundred and sixty (960) teachers (480 teachers from District Mardan and 480 teachers from District Swabi) of urban and rural areas were randomly selected from 96 secondary schools. The questionnaire was used in data collection. The researcher visited the sample's schools personally to get the appropriate information through the use of selected instruments. i.e. questionnaires. The teachers were instructed about the method of questionnaire filling. The respondents (teachers) marked on the suitable place one of the five categories ranging from "very negative effect to high effect" carrying the score 5 to 1 respectively, and also on another suitable place one of the three categories ranging from excellent to not satisfactory or other given option, carrying the score from 3 to 1. The coded data was tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted category wise as teachers by utilizing descriptive and inferential statistical techniques such as frequency, Percentage, and ANOVA to get the true picture of the prevailing factors affecting quality education among the public secondary schools of District Mardan and Swabi and also analyzed by using SPSS. Questionnaire was developed after consulting relevant literature and it was pilot tested also to know about its validity and reliability. Many changes in the items of questionnaire were made as per suggestions taken from experts of the field and after calculation of co-relations coefficient value though Cronbach alpha. Similarly, ethical guidelines were followed before collection of data from teachers. A permission from concerned district Education Officers (male & female) of both districts were soughted in the

first phase, in the next phase, permission from heads of the schools were also taken and in the last purpose of the research was also share with teachers along with all other stakeholder. After getting willingness of the teachers to become part of this study, their point of views or perceptions were taken. Same procedure for both male and female teachers was adopted. From female as a cultural hurdle, a female research assistant was hired and data was collected.

Results and Conclusions

Table:1: Opinions of teachers about management-related factors affecting quality education

Sr no	Aspects	Level in schools			Comparison group	Comparative effectiveness Mean (i-j)	F	P values
		Often (Oft)	Sometimes (SmT)	Never (Nv)				
1	There is an effective school management style	493 (51%)	414 (43%)	53 (6%)	Oft&Sm T	.86*	467.21	.00
Oft&Nv 2.86*					SmT&Nv 1.99*			
2	Our school is a safe, clean, and well maintained	568 (60%)	348 (36%)	44 (04%)	Oft&Sm T	1.04*	472.29	.00
Oft&Nv 2.64*					SmT&Nv 1.59*			
3	The principal compliments both teachers and students in their work	486 (51%)	422 (44%)	52 (5%)	Oft&Sm T	.78*	298.35	.00
Oft&Nv 2.32*					SmT&Nv 1.53*			
4	Teachers have ease of access to the principal to discuss problems	652 (68%)	261 (27%)	47 (5%)	Oft&Sm T	.86*	449.47	.00
Oft&Nv 2.65*					SmT&Nv 1.79*			
5	Teachers come to the class on time	736 (77%)	203 (21%)	21 (2%)	Oft&Sm T	1.76*	573.11	.00
Oft&Nv 2.26*					SmT&Nv .49*			
6	Teachers leave the class on time	702 (73%)	241 (25%)	17 (2%)	Oft&Sm T	1.22*	162.36	.00
Oft&Nv 1.59*					SmT&Nv .37			

*significant at the 0.05 level

Table 1 indicates the effect of management-related factors on quality education. For the first factor, the statistical values show that 51% of schools had an effective school management style with a level of “often”, 43% with “sometimes”, and 06 % with a “never”, level in this aspect. Furthermore, the values from the Post-Hoc test indicate that schools having an effective school management style with a level of “often”, were significantly ($P<0.05$) contributing in educational quality than the schools with “sometimes”, and “never”, level. Similarly, the schools with an effective school management style having the level of “sometimes”, were significantly contributing to quality education as compared to schools with “never”, level ($i-j=1.99, P<0.05$).

For 2nd factor, showing school is safe, clean and well maintained, the statistical values show that 60% of schools had safe, clean and well maintained with the level of “often”, 36% with ‘sometimes’, and 04% with “never”, level in this aspect. Furthermore, the values from Post-Hoc test indicate that schools having a safe, clean and well-maintained environment, with the level of “often” were significantly ($P<0.05$) contributing in educational

quality than the schools with “sometimes”, and “never”, level. Similarly, the schools having a safe, clean and well-maintained environment, with the level of “sometimes”, were significantly contributing in quality education as compared to schools with “never”, level ($i-j=1.59, P<0.05$).

For the third factor, showing the principal give complement to both teachers and students in their work, the statistical values show that 51% of schools had a principal who gives compliments to both teachers and students in their work with a level of “often”, 44% with “sometimes”, and 05% with “never”, level in this aspect. Furthermore, the values from the Post-Hoc test indicate that schools with a principal who give a compliment to both teachers and students in their work having the level of “often”, were significantly ($P<0.05$) contributing in educational quality than the schools with “sometimes”, and “never”, level. Similarly, the schools with the principal who give complement to both teachers and students in their work having the level of “sometimes”, were significantly contributing in quality education as compared to schools with “never”, level ($i-j=1.53, P<0.05$).

For the 4th factor, showing the teachers who have ease of access to the principal to discuss the problems, the statistical values show that 68% of schools with teachers having an ease of access to the principal had the level of “often”, 27% with “sometimes”, and 05% with “never”, level in this aspect. Furthermore, the values from the Post-Hoc test indicate that schools with teachers having an ease of access to the principal with the level of “often”, were significantly ($P<0.05$) contributing in educational quality than the schools with a level of “sometimes”, and “never”, level. Similarly, the schools with teachers having an ease of access to the principal having a level of “sometimes” were significantly contributing to quality education as compared to schools with “never”, level ($i-j=1.79, P<0.05$).

For the 5th factor, showing teachers who come to the class on time, the statistical values show that 77% of schools had teachers who prefer to come to the class on time having a level of “often”, 21% with “sometimes”, and 02% with “never”, level in this aspect. Furthermore, the values from the Post-Hoc test indicate that schools with teachers who prefer to come to the class on time having the level of “often”, were significantly ($P<0.05$) contributing in educational quality than the schools with “sometimes”, and “never”, level. Similarly, the schools with teachers who come to the class on time having a level of “sometimes”, were significantly contributing to quality education as compared to schools with “never”, level ($i-j=.49, P<0.05$).

For the 6th factor, showing teachers leave the class on time; the statistical values show that 73% of schools had teachers who prefer to leave the class on time with the level of “often”, 25% with “sometimes”, and 02% with “never”, level in this aspect. Furthermore, the values from the Post-Hoc test indicate that schools with teachers who prefer to leave the class on time having a level of “often”, were significantly ($P<0.05$) contributing in educational quality than the schools with the “sometimes”, and “never”, levels. Similarly, the schools with teachers who leave the class on time having the level of “sometimes”, were significantly contributing to quality education as compared to schools with “never” level ($i-j=.37, P<0.05$).

Table:2: Opinions of teachers about financial power-related factors affecting quality education

Sr. no.	Aspects	Level in schools			Comparison Group	Comparative effectiveness Mean (i-j)	F	P values
		To Great Extent (TagE)	a To Extent (time)	To some Not at all (Natal)				
1	The quality of physical facilities.	76 (8%)	832 (87%)	52 (5%)	TagE&TsmE TagE&Natal TsmE&Natal (F=P<0.05)	.52* 1.95* 1.43*	82.61	.00
2	There is an effective system of security.	89 (10%)	819 (85%)	52 (5%)	TagE&TsmE TagE&Natal TsmE&Natal (F=P<0.05)	.59* 2.78* 2.19*	191.18	.00
3	A.V. Aids facility is available for teachers.	108 (11%)	493 (51%)	359 (38%)	TagE&TsmE TagE&Natal TsmE&Natal (F=P<0.05)	-.39* 1.86* 2.25*	631.44	.00
4	A transport facility is available for teachers.	91 (10%)	232 (24%)	637 (66%)	TagE&TsmE TagE&Natal TsmE&Natal (F=P<0.05)	-.31 1.35* 1.66*	223.73	.00

5.	A scholarship facility is available for brilliant students	102 (11%)	425 (44%)	433 (45%)	TagE&TsmE TagE&Natal TsmE&Natal (F=P<0.05)	-.06 2.17* 2.23*	578. 31	.00
----	--	--------------	--------------	--------------	---	------------------------	------------	-----

*significant at the 0.05 level

Table 2 indicates the effect of financial power-related factors on quality education. The statistical values show that 87% of schools had the proper building, sufficient classrooms, etc. having the level of “to some extent”, 08% with “to a great extent”, and 05% with “not at all” in this aspect. Furthermore, the values from the Post-Hoc test indicate that schools with proper physical facilities, having a level of “to some extent”, were significantly ($P<0.05$) contributing in educational quality than the schools with “to a great extent”, and “not at all”, level. Similarly, the schools with physical facilities having a level of “to a great extent”, were significantly contributing to quality education as compared to schools with “not at all”, levels ($i-j=1.49$, $P<0.05$).

For 2nd factor, showing an effective system of security measures to ensure a secure learning environment, the statistical values show that 85% of schools had an effective system of security having the level of “to some extent”, 10% with “to a great extent”, and 05% with “not at all”, level in this aspect. Furthermore, the values from the Post-Hoc test indicate that schools having a level of “to some extent”, were significantly ($P<0.05$) contributing in educational quality than schools with “to a great extent”, and “not at all”, level. Similarly, the schools with an effective system of security having a level of “to a great extent”, were significantly contributing to quality education as compared to schools with “not at all”, level ($i-j=2.19$, $P<0.05$).

For the third factor, showing A.V. Aids facilities is available for teachers; the statistical values show that 51% of schools had an A.V. Aids facility having the level of “to some extent”, 38% with “not at all”, and 11% with “to a great extent”, level in this aspect. Furthermore, the values from the Post-Hoc test indicate that schools having A.V. Aids facilities are available for teachers with a level of “to some extent”, were significantly ($P<0.05$) contributing in educational quality than the schools with a level of “to a great extent”, and “not at all”. Similarly, the schools with A.V. Aids facilities having a level of “to a great extent” were significantly contributing to quality education as compared to schools with “not at all”, levels ($i-j=2.25$, $P<0.05$).

For the fourth factor, showing transport facility is available for teachers, the statistical values show that 66% schools had transport facility with the level of “not at all”, 24% with “to some extent” and 10% with “to a great extent”, level in this aspect. Furthermore, the values from the Post-Hoc test indicate that schools where transport facilities are available for teachers having the level of “to a great extent”, there were no significant differences ($P>0.05$) in educational quality than the schools with a level of “to some extent”, and “not at all”, level. Similarly, the schools with transport facilities having a level of “to some extent” were significantly contributing to quality education as compared to schools with “not at all”, level ($i-j=1.66$, $P<0.05$).

For the 5th factor, showing scholarship facility is available for brilliant students, the statistical values show that 45% of schools with scholarship facility are available for students having the level of “not at all”, 44% with “to some extent”, and 11% with “to a great extent” in this aspect. Furthermore, the values from the Post-Hoc test indicate that schools having scholarship facility is available for brilliant students with a level of “to a great extent”, were not significantly contributing ($P>0.05$) in educational quality than the schools with “to some extent”, and “not at all”, level. Similarly, the schools with scholarship facilities are available having the level of “to some extent”, were significantly contributing to quality education as compared to schools with “not at all”, level ($i-j=2.23$, $P<0.05$).

This study has concluded that there is no facility of scholarship for the brilliant students, so it is not the significant factor of quality education. Transport is the basic need for the students and teachers but in this study it shows that this factor is also non significant for the quality education at the secondary level in public sector. This study indicated that there is an effective school management style that offers a conducive environment for teaching and learning. Overall environment of school e.g., safe, clean, and well maintained are the significant factors of quality education. It was also find out that the principal compliments both teachers and students in their work, teachers have ease of access to the principal to discuss problems, teachers come to the class on time, and teachers leave the class on time are the significant factors of quality education. The quality of physical facilities (proper buildings, sufficient classrooms, labs) affects the quality of education in our school. There is an effective system of security measures to ensure a secure learning environment for teachers and these are the significant factors of the quality education. Nowadays the technological fluctuations and due to technological progress, audio visual aids have become an important source of providing lecture more competently and efficiently. The study revealed that availability of A.V. aids is the significant of quality of education.

The Way Forward

In the light of this study, the following recommendations were made based on findings and conclusion:

1. The government may provide opportunities of capacity development of teachers in the use of finances of the schools effectively so that they may perform well whenever they get the chance to become principals or heads of the schools.

2. The government may develop the capacity of all schools' heads in management of schools affairs including the finances at the earliest.
3. The government may develop a policy to assign the responsibility of leadership of schools to those only who may have the capacity to run the schools more effectively.
4. The government may develop a policy to appoint or promote teachers as principals on the basis of their knowledge and skills to become a leader not on the basis of their seniority or length of job.
5. The Government may provide the transport facilities for the teachers because they may be able to reach their schools on time.
6. The Government may bound the principals to create a conducive environment for teaching and learning in the school.
7. The government may ensure the security system in the schools that the principal, teachers, and the students may be able to feel secure and study with full concentration.
8. The government is demanded that to provide all the kinds of infrastructure in the schools with well-equipped materials.
9. The government is suggested to provide the audio-visual facilities for the teachers to use the AV aids during teaching so it will be very effective for the students.

References

- Adesina, S. (1990). Educational Management. Nigeria: Fourth Dimension Publishing.
- Baraka, Y.K., (2010). Challenges Facing Public Secondary School Principals in Financial Management: A Case Study of Kitui District, Nairobi: Kenyatta University Library, Unpublished M.Ed Thesis.
- Doherty, G. D. (2008). On Quality in Education: *Quality Assurance in Education*, 16 (3), 2-8.
- Education Management Information System, (2016-17). *Government of KPK, Elementary & Secondary Education Department* retrieved on 25th August 2014. <http://www.kpese.gov.pk/home/view.cfm?MenuID1>
- Education System in Pakistan Problems. Issues & Solutions, *pgc.edu*. 17 November 2017.
- Government of Kenya, (2006). A handbook of financial management, Nairobi; government printer https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Districts_of_Khyber_Pakhtunkhwa imperative. Paris: UNESCO.
- Kathleen, D. (2003). A Qualitative Study of Factors that Influence the Decisions Regarding Assessment of Students' Competence in Practice Caledonian Nursing and Midwifery Research Centre, 98.
- Kuria L.K., (2012). Budgeting Process and Financial Management in Public Secondary Schools in Thika District, Kenya. Nairobi: Unpublished M.Ed Thesis; Kenyatta University Library.
- Ministry of Education. (2005). Education Sector Development Program –III. 2005/006 2010/2011. Program Action Plan. Addis Ababa: Berhanena Selam Printing Enterprise.
- Munyiri, C.W. (2008). Failing Management in Kenyan Schools, Nairobi: In the website, <http://www.kenyaimagine.com>.
- Nyamwea, J.O.W. (2006). An Investigation of the effectiveness of Accounting Control System in Educational Institutions: a case study of public secondary schools in Homabay and Rachwonyo District, Unpublished MBA Dissertation, Kenyatta University.
- Nyongesa, J.N. (2007). Educational Administration, Nairobi: Jomo Kenyatta Foundation publishers Odidi D.O. (2002). The effect of finances on the quality of learning, Nairobi; Kenyatta university press.
- Pakistan Bureau of Statistic, (2017). Enumeration of the Pakistani population, 15th March, 2017 to 25th May 2017. peoplelearn.homestead.com/principainstructleader.htm.
- Phillip, J. A. (2011). Manager-Administrator to Instructional Leader: Shift in the Role of School Principal. Retrieved on June 27, 2011. Available at:
- Shami P. A., & Hussain, K. S. (2005). *Development of Education in Pakistan. Academy of Educational Planning and Management Ministry of Education* (AEPAM Research Study No. 183) Islamabad, Pakistan.
- Sharma, D., & Kamath, R. (2006). *Quality in Education*, Kalpaz Publication Delhi.
- United Nation Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, (1990). *The World Declaration on Education for All* (Available at www.unesco.org)
- United Nation Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, (2004). *The quality*
- WAIM (2013). Beidaihe, China, June 14-16, 2013: proceedings. Berlin: Springer.
- Wang, J. (2013). *Web-age information management 14th International Conference*,

Author Information

Muhammad Tayyab

PhD scholar Hazara University Mansehra

Dr. Muhammad Amjid

Assistant Professor, Cadet College Swat

Dr. Asaf Niwaz

Associate Professor, The University of Haripur

Dr. Javed IqbalAssistant Professor Hazara University Mansehra
